

Damage Zones and their Growth in Sandwich Composites under Hull Slamming Loading Conditions

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SUMMARY

Delamination failure in sandwich composites under hull slamming conditions led to the investigation of bimaterial cracks. Full field stress distribution around a crack was analyzed using thermoelastic stress analysis. The measured temperature field shows a discontinuity across the interface of bimaterials, illustrating potential application of this method to study damage.

Keywords: hull slamming, sandwich structure, composite, damage, bimaterial, thermal imaging

MOTIVATION

There is increasing interest in using composite materials, particularly sandwich structures, in the production of high speed marine craft. The high strength to weight capability inherent in composite materials allows for the design of lighter and faster craft. These lightweight high speed craft can experience substantial wave loading at rates much higher than in other sea craft. This "hull slamming" loading is characterized by periodic yet intense transient loading. Understanding the fatigue and damage response of sandwich composites to this type of loading is crucial for the design of safe, long lasting vehicles. The objective of this investigation is to analyze and record the evolution of delamination and other failure mechanisms in sandwich structures due to dynamic low cycle fatigue loading conditions.

INTRODUCTION

In order to characterize the response of sandwich structures under repeated transient loading, this research involved observing damage evolution and characterizing stresses in sandwich structures and composite materials. The experimental apparatus utilized in this research include a custom built facility to simulate hull slamming conditions experienced by marine craft, a MTS servo hydraulic testing machine, and a high sensitivity FLIR Thermovision SC6000 focal plane array infrared thermal camera. The custom made slamming device was used to impart loads replicating hull slamming on sandwich composite samples, while the infrared camera recorded the temperature evolution of the sample. In order to obtain full field stress patterns, a technique known

as Thermoelastic Stress Analysis (TSA) was implemented to correlate the measured temperature variation to applied stress variation. Several bimaterial cracked specimens were tested in a servo-hydraulic materials testing machine to demonstrate the ability of the TSA method to measure the full field stress distribution. This method is being currently extended to study damage evolution in sandwich structures.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Hull slamming simulator

A hull slamming facility (Figure 1) has been designed which imparts characteristic loads via a pneumatic piston to produce repeatable pulses simulating wave slamming conditions on specimens of interest. Theoretical pressure distributions from wedge slamming studies [1] and experiments [2] were used in the design process of the hull slamming facility.

Figure 1. Mechanical hull slamming simulator.

Thermal Imaging

Thermal imaging techniques including pulsed phase thermography and thermoelastic stress analysis (TSA) can reveal the presence of damage within the composite samples. By interrupting the cyclic loading experiments at various times and analyzing the thermal response, one can correlate the extent of damage as a function of loading duration. In the damage zones, friction and nonlinear material effects increase the temperature of the surrounding material. The various failure processes can be tracked *in-situ* by imaging the zone of increased temperature using a high resolution thermal camera. A better understanding of the damage mechanisms can help guide the development of models for predicting damage evolution under hull slamming conditions leading to better life prediction.

TSA is an application of thermal imaging utilizing the thermoelastic effect to determine a full field stress pattern and a review of the method can be found in [3]. The thermoelastic effect is the temperature variation due to the sum of the principal stresses ($\sigma_x + \sigma_y$) and for a homogeneous, isotropic material is given by the equation below.

$$\Delta T = -\frac{\alpha T}{\rho C_p} \Delta(\sigma_x + \sigma_y) \quad (1)$$

where α is the thermal expansion coefficient, ρ is the density, C_p is the specific heat, T is the absolute temperature. Previously, this method has been used to measure the temperature variation and determine the stress intensity factor at a crack tip in homogenous materials [4] and for cracks oriented at various angles [5].

SANDWICH SLAMMING CHARACTERIZATION

A sandwich composite was subject to cyclic loading in the hull slamming simulator. The temperature evolution of the foam in the sample was recorded with the thermal camera and evidence of damage is visible in Figure 2 near the foam-skin interface. The delamination failure mode is a common mode of failure in sandwich composites and a better understanding of this occurrence can help predict such damage growth.

Figure 2. Temperature in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a sandwich composite under slamming loading.

BIMATERIAL CRACK

Since delamination failures often occur at bimaterial interfaces, measuring the stress distribution at bimaterial crack interfaces can provide insight into their expected growth. In order to study this problem, simplified geometries were created with interface cracks machined between different isotropic materials with known geometry as shown in Figure 3. These samples were loaded in the MTS servo-hydraulic testing machine under displacement control. The materials chosen were nylon and acrylic for their relatively high thermoelastic response.

Figure 3. Bimaterial crack geometries: material 1 is nylon, material 2 is acrylic.

Calibration

These bimaterial samples were cyclically loaded in tension and the recorded thermal images give the variation in temperature due to thermoelasticity. In order to convert the temperature variation into a stress field, separate calibrations for these materials are needed to convert the temperature variation map into a stress field. Block samples of the particular nylon and acrylic used were cyclically loaded in the MTS servo-hydraulic machine to excite the thermoelastic response and allow averaging techniques to improve the results. Using the measured force variation from the MTS machine and the average thermal variation from the infrared camera, two calibration curves were developed as shown in Figures 4 and 5 for acrylic and nylon respectively.

Figure 4. Calibration of acrylic.

Figure 5. Calibration of nylon.

These materials have a very linear thermoelastic response, as expected, with a factor of 95 converting temperature variation in Celsius into stress in MPa for Acrylic and 85 for Nylon. This difference in thermoelastic response can be seen in the bimaterial crack temperature field in Figure 6, where we can see a discontinuity in the temperature field along the 0.15 °C contour. Within each material, these curves represent a constant sum of principle stresses. The cracked sample was cyclically loaded at 5Hz in tension perpendicular to the interface.

Figure 6. Temperature Variation in °C for a bimaterial edge crack with $a/w = 0.5$.

Thermal stress analysis (TSA) results

The temperature field near a center crack on a bimaterial interface is shown in Figure 7 with loading in tension perpendicular to the interface. It is observed that one side of the crack sustained higher stress than the other, which likely came from asymmetries in the sample or loading. There is good agreement between the measured temperature variation or equivalently stress field with a finite element model reporting the sum of principal stresses.

Figure 7. Left: Temperature field near bimaterial center crack with $a/w = 0.25$;
Right: Sum of principal stresses from FEA simulation.

In Fig. 7, one can observe a non zero stress region along the crack free surface. This region carries no tension load but does sustain lateral compression of the plate as it is loaded in tension. The TSA data also reveals that this region is in compression by comparing the phase to the far field.

CONCLUSIONS

The results from this work show that the TSA method is capable of resolving stress distributions near a crack tip along a bimaterial interface. There is potential for measuring stress intensity factors at bimaterial interfaces, particularly in sandwich structures. Analysis of stress patterns can be extended to more complex composite materials and aid in development of damage models in sandwich structures under transient loading conditions as those corresponding to hull slamming in marine structures. The stress analysis aided by thermal imaging together with other measurement techniques will greatly enhance the ability to characterize damage zones and their growth in sandwich/composite structures.

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References

1. R. Zhao and O. M. Faltinsen, "Water entry of two-dimensional bodies", *J. Fluid. Mech.* 246, 593-612 (1993)
2. M. Battley and S. Lake, "Dynamic performance of sandwich core materials", *Proceedings of the 16th International conference on composite materials, Kyoto, Japan* (2007)
3. J. M. Dulieu-Barton, T. R. Emery, S. Quinn¹ and P. R. Cunningham, "A temperature correction methodology for quantitative thermoelastic stress analysis and damage assessment", *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 17, 1627-1637 (2006)
4. J. R. Lesniak, D. J. Bazile, B. R. Boyce, M. J. Zickel, K. E. Kramer and C. S. Welch, "Stress intensity measurement via infrared focal plane array", *ASTM STP No. 1318*, 208-220, ASTM (1997)
5. J.M. Dulieu-Barton, M. Fulton and P. Stanley, "The analysis of thermoelastic isopachic data from crack tip stress fields", *Fatig. Fract. Engng. Mater. Struct.* 23, 301 - 314 (2001)